

RNA22 v2 results

Results have been computed and are shown below. If there are no results shown, it means your chosen parameters yielded no results.

Note: The p-value represents the likelihood that the target site loci is random. That is, a lower p-value represents a greater chance that the loci contains a valid MRE

miR Name	transcript name	leftmost position of predicted target site	folding energy (in -Kcal/mol)	heteroduplex	p value
hsa_mir_143	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	117	-13.30	ACACAGCTGCCTCCAGC-CTACACC TG-GTC--TCTACGTCGTGACGTGG	1.02E-2
hsa_mir_143	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	766	-19.80	TTCAGACACTGTCGCCCTGCACA : : TGGTCT-CTACG-TCGTGACGTGG	5.73E-2
hsa_mir_143	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	935	-14.90	TCCTCTGA-GCAGACAAAGTGACCC TGGTCTCTACG-TC-GT--GACGTGG	1.74E-1
hsa_mir_143	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	2314	-20.90	TGCAGTACGGCAGCTTCTGCACC TGGTCTCTACGTCG-TGACGTGG	1.89E-1
let_7a_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	107	-13.30	GACCACCAGAACACAGCTGCCTCC : : : TTG-ATATGTTG-GATGATGGAGT	1.02E-2
let_7a_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	1506	-15.70	GGCT--TCAAC-TGCTACTTCC : : : TTGATATGTTGGATGATGGAGT	5.19E-3
let_7a_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	1600	-15.00	AACTGCTGATGCC-CCTGCCACA : : : : TTGAT-ATGT-TGGATGATGGAGT	5.91E-2
let_7a_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	2623	-17.50	GACTG-ACAG--TGCTGCCTCC : : : : TTGATATGTTGGATGATGGAGT	1.35E-2
mir_101_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	813	-18.20	AGCAGCAGCGGATG-GACAGCTG : : TCGTAGTCGT-GACACTATTGAC	5.73E-2
mir_101_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	2876	-15.00	AGCA--AGCGCCTGGAAAGCTG : : TCGTAGTCGTG--ACACTATTGAC	9.97E-3
mir_101_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	3862	-12.60	TGCA-CTACAC-ATGATGACTC : TCGTAGTCGTGACACTATTGAC	2.44E-3
mir_145_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	3490	-15.30	ACAGCTTCAAAGAGGAACTGGAC : TCCCTAAGGACCCCTTTGACCTG	8.35E-2
mir_15a_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	2298	-13.00	TGC--TCCA--ACCTGCTGCTG : : GTGTTGGTAATACACGACGAT	2.49E-1

miR Name	transcript name	leftmost position of predicted target site	folding energy (in -Kcal/mol)	heteroduplex	p value
mir_15b_3p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	1965	-14.60	ACCGGCAGCAA--TGTGTTTCA : : ATCTCGTCGTTATTACTAAGC	1.21E-1
mir_15b_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	2296	-14.70	AGTGCTCCA--ACCTGCTGCTG : : ACATTTGGTACTACACGACGAT	2.49E-1
mir_15b_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	3754	-17.30	TGTGTTGCATGACCAGTCTGCTG : : ACATTTGGTACTACACGACGAT	1.42E-1
mir_16_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	55	-14.60	TGTTGTTCTCTGCTGCTGCTG : : : GCCGTTATAA-ATGCACGACGAT	2.89E-1
mir_200a_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	3122	-13.60	TCTGGC-C--GCCACCAAGATG AGGTCGTGACAGGCCATTCTAC	2.85E-1
mir_200b_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	3122	-13.60	TCT--GGCCGCC-ACCAAGATG : AGGTTACGACGGGTATTCTAC	2.85E-1
mir_21_3p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	163	-14.50	ACTACCC--CGACAAGTGTTC TGTCGGGTAGCTG-ACCACAAAC	3.06E-1
mir_21_3p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	1568	-22.70	TCAGCCCTACAGAGTGGTGGTG TGTCGGG-TAGTGACCACAAAC	7.85E-2
mir_21_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	2874	-12.90	ACAGCAAGCGCCCTGGGAAAGCTG : : : : AGTTGT-AGTCAGACT-ATTCGAT	9.97E-3
mir_21_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	3187	-13.50	AGGGCTACCACCTGATGAGCTT : : AGTTGTAGTCAGACTATTGAT	3.38E-1
mir_29a_3p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	55	-13.20	TGTTGTTCTC--CTGGTCTG : : ATTGGCTAAAGTCTACCACGAT	2.89E-1
mir_29a_3p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	1569	-17.09	CAGCCCTACAGAGTGGTGGTCTG : : : ATTGG--CTAAAGTCTACCACGAT	7.85E-2
mir_29a_3p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	1690	-15.50	TGACCCGACCCGG--CGTGCTG : : : ATTGGCTAAAGTCTACCACGAT	4.82E-2
mir_34a_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	108	-17.82	ACCACCAG-AACACAGTGCCT : TGTTGGTCGATTCTGTGACGGT	1.02E-2
mir_34a_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	757	-17.60	TCACCCGGTTTCAGACACTGCTG : : : : TGTTGGTCGA-TTCTGTGACGGT	5.73E-2
mir_34a_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	1066	-14.60	TCGGCGAGGTG-TTCAATGCCA : : TGTTGGTCGATTCTGTGACGGT	2.81E-1
mir_34a_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	1338	-19.10	TTACCCGCTGTGTGATTGCCT : : : : TGTTGGTCGATTCTGTGACGGT	1.69E-1
mir_34a_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	1598	-13.80	CGAACT-GCTGCATGCCCTGCCA : : :	5.91E-2

